

A MODEL OF AFFECTIVE, COGNITIVE AND HEDONIC RESPONSE TO PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the user response to product features, within the context of a non-instrumental interaction. Basing on existing literature, three types of response are identified: cognitive, hedonic and emotional response. This work proposes a visual model in which the different types of user response, their relations and the processes underlying their elicitation are represented. The suggested model is an attempt to give an overview of the aspects involved in the generation of the user response and their mutual influences, with the aim to support researchers in the field of Design and Emotion in clarifying the context of their studies.

Possible uses of the model are discussed, both as a theoretical framework and as a practical research tool. Moreover, various disciplines involved in the study of this many-sided phenomenon are placed on the model, with a particular focus on the role of design.

Keywords: product design, user response, cognition, emotions, pleasure.

INTRODUCTION

In studying emotional reactions to products, or to any kind of artifact, it is impossible to clearly separate the level of emotion from the one of cognition. These two levels of the human experience are strictly related and mutually affect each other (Norman, 2004). This statement justifies the presence, in the Design and Emotion field, of a lot of studies, methods and tools, concerning not only emotions, but any aspects of the user response to products (see, for instance, the tools and methods proposed by the Design and Emotion

Society). Among others, these studies deal with sensory and multisensory perception, meaning association, metaphors creation, product personality attribution and other 'soft' aspects of the user-product interaction, basically cognitive, instead of emotional. The wide range of tools and methods developed to study different aspects of the user response offers a realistic view of the complexity of this phenomenon, which is referred to with the name of 'product experience' (Hekkert, 2006; Desmet and Hekkert, 2007).

Although different studies focus on specific aspects of the product experience, the lack of a comprehensive view of the steps composing the generation of the different levels of experience and their relation, makes it difficult to clearly understand how to control the design process in order to generate the intended response. Moreover, the presence of a number of disciplines involved in the analysis of these topics, from marketing to philosophy, increases the confusion around the issue of the user response generated within the user-product interaction.

Desmet and Hekkert (2007) propose a framework of product experience, in which three levels are identified: aesthetic experience, experience of meaning and emotional experience. Norman (2004) suggests a different categorization of the three levels of the user response, classifying them as visceral, behavioural and reflective levels. In both frameworks, the content of the levels is put in relation to the aspects that affect each type of experience, but little is explained about the real processes which underlie the generation of these responses.

Studies in the field of neuroscience allowed to discover the neurological processes which occur in the elaboration of the stimuli coming from the

environment (Damasio, 1994; Le Doux, 1996). The knowledge emerged could give further support in the study of the user response, completing the conceptual models already present in literature with detailed information about the neurological processes, useful also for design research. To confirm this view, some authors apply this approach to the field of design, stressing the importance of studying “affective response to the perception of an object as modeled in affective neuroscience” (Christoforidou and Motte, 2009).

Neuroscience can offer new knowledge about what occurs in the user at an unconscious level during the user-product interaction, also helping to measure aspects of the user response such as the level of arousal a product causes, the activation of the pleasure system or the stimulation of the emotional centres. This discipline also provides different methods and tools for the study of the user affective reactions to products, through indirect and objective instruments (fMRI, EEG, eye tracking, etc.), which do not require self-reports by the user about his affective and emotional states, as it happens for the traditional cognitive psychology instruments (Desmet, 2004). For these reasons, advances in neuroscience could open new frontiers in the area of Design and Emotion, as the most recent tendencies in this field demonstrate (Jenkins et al., 2009).

OBJECTIVES

The aim of the present work is to propose a possible overview of the different levels of the user response, how they are generated and their mutual relations. The attempt is to combine the perspective of affective neuroscience with the models about user response existing in literature. The suggested framework wants to represent, through a visual map, the main steps composing the process of elaboration of the information which come from the product, showing at what stage each type of response emerges. However, its scope is not just to reflect the real process from the stimulus capture to the response generation, but to create a useful tool for further research. Theories about these issues are still debated and there are no indisputable certainties. As Christoforidou and Motte (2009) maintain, “models in design research are not intended to be “true” to reality (realism), but to be useful (instrumentalism)”.

By reviewing existing literature and proposing it as a coherent model, the following objectives are intended to be achieved:

- to visually represent the relations between the different types of responses, what are they determined by and their mutual influences.
- to create a helpful tool for researchers in the field of Design and Emotion, to clarify the placement of their own studies in this broad area, and their relation to the other components of the user response.
- to identify the disciplines facing these themes, and their areas of interest. This way it would be possible to stress the role of design in the study of this topic, and its relation with different disciplines.

In order to complete these task, a literature review was performed to clarify the different types of response, on the basis of the models and theories by different authors. Subsequently, a review of the main theories about the neural mechanisms underlying the response generation was accomplished. Finally, a model was created to put in relation the process of the user response generation with the types of response and their content.

The possible uses of the model were stressed, both as a tool to facilitate the comprehension of this field of research and as an active instrument of research. It is important to underline that the model proposed relates to the response generated by the perception of the ‘product form’, intended as the product physical features, related to visual, tactile, sound and smell properties (Bloch, 1995; Crilly et al., 2004). It thus describes the response emerging by a non-instrumental interaction, i.e. an interaction not aimed at the product use (Desmet and Hekkert, 2007).

THREE TYPES OF USER RESPONSE

The first step in the construction of a comprehensive model of the user response consists of a literature review, aimed to summarize and review the main classifications of the user response. Basically, this review relies on the models proposed by Desmet and Hekkert (2007), Crilly et al. (2004) and Norman (2004). All these authors subdivide the user response to product (or ‘product experience’) into three levels, not identical, but showing some similarities.

On the basis of these references, here a slightly different classification is proposed, composed by three types of response: the cognitive response, the hedonic response and the emotional response. It is important to underline that the considered types of response are all psychological responses; they are often followed by behavioural reactions, as Desmet and Hekkert maintain: “affective experiences initiate behavioural tendencies like approach, inaction, avoidance, and attack” (Desmet and Hekkert, 2007). Bloch describes these behavioural reactions towards a product with the concept of approach and avoidance (Bloch, 1995).

COGNITIVE RESPONSE

The first type of response relates to cognitive elaborations. Cognition is our evaluation system able to interpret and make sense of what we perceive. Cognitive response to product concerns the processes described by Crilly et al. (2004) as semantic interpretation and symbolic association. In semantic interpretation, the stimulus is recognized and interpreted and a meaning is assigned to it. This kind of response also comprises the four semantic functions of products: describe, express, signal, identify (Mono, Demirbilek and Sener, 2003). Symbolic association “is determined by what the product is seen to symbolize about its user, or the socio-cultural context of use” (Crilly et al., 2004). Desmet and Hekkert call this level *experience of meaning*: “through cognitive processes, like interpretation, memory retrieval, and associations, we are able to recognize metaphors, assign personality or other expressive characteristics, and assess the personal or symbolic significance of products” (Desmet and Hekkert, 2007). This level of response is strongly influenced by all the cultural and social references, together with the previous experiences of the user. Note that Crilly et al. (2004) add the level of *aesthetic impression* to cognitive response; the same level corresponds to the *aesthetic experience* in Desmet and Hekkert, which is considered here as a separate level, i.e. the hedonic response.

HEDONIC RESPONSE

The second level of the response relates to the pleasure elicited by a product. Pleasure can be

primary connected to the perception of product features, which may stimulate one or more sensory modalities, generating a pleasant sensation (Desmet and Hekkert, 2007; Norman, 2004; Ramachandran, 1999). The visual, tactile, sound or olfactory properties of objects may delight senses, resulting in the generation of a type of hedonic response, called by Jordan *physio-pleasure* (Jordan, 1997; 2000). However, pleasure is not connected just to sensory perception. Jordan, basing on Tiger (1992) identifies other classes of pleasure aroused by products, two of whom are particularly interesting for a non-instrumental interaction: *socio-pleasure* and *ideo-pleasure* (Jordan, 1997; 2000); they will be better explained in the next sections of the paper.

The relation between pleasure and emotion has been debated in the last decades. Some authors argue that pleasure can be defined as an emotion itself, others consider it as a parameter to categorize emotions - which can be pleasant or unpleasant (Helander and Khalid, 2006, p.555). Anyway, literature specifically focusing on pleasure in product perception and use is quite extensive, and supports the choice of considering it an independent level of the user response, with its own structure. This view is confirmed also by the fact that, in our brain, pleasure is associated to specific centres (Christoforidou and Motte, 2009). The feeling of pleasure can thus be considered different from the concept of emotion, which is much more complex, although they are mutually influencing and, in some cases, overlapping.

EMOTIONAL RESPONSE

The last level of the user response concerns the emotional reaction towards a product. Interacting with products causes a wide range of emotions, connected to the product's appearance, functions, behaviour and associated meanings (Desmet, 2003). Desmet (2003) proposes a classification of the emotions elicited by products, divided into five categories: surprise, instrumental, aesthetic, social and interest emotions. Most literature about emotions elicited by products bases on the theories of cognitive psychology, in particular the appraisal theory (Lazarus, 1991). Many authors argue that emotions are the result of a cognitive process, in which the stimulus is evaluated on the basis of the user's concerns (goals, needs, beliefs etc.) (Desmet, 2003; Desmet and Hekkert,

2007; Demir et al, 2009). As Desmet and Hekkert (2007) maintain, “an emotion is thus the result of a cognitive, though often automatic and unconscious, process.”

If we compare this model to those developed in other fields of research, some contradictions emerge.

Indeed, appraisal theory seems to be in contrast with the model deriving from the neuroscience studies, according to which emotions precede and affect cognitive processes (Damasio, 1994; LeDoux, 1996; Christoforidou and Motte, 2009).

Actually, the term emotion is used indifferently to relate to two separate reactions, both affective, but intrinsically different. These two types of emotions are called primary and secondary emotions (Damasio, 1994; Picard, 1997; Christoforidou and Motte, 2009).

Neuroscience models relate to primary emotions, while appraisal theory concerns secondary emotions. This distinction has to be carefully considered when approaching literature on this topic.

Primary emotions

Primary, or *visceral* (Picard, 1997), emotions are automatic reactions, elicited directly by a stimulus which activates the brain areas responsible for affective judgments, very fast and instinctive (Helander and Khalid, 2006). These emotions are often essential in helping the human survival, because they “exist to make the person more reactive to its environment”. Indeed, “Affect disrupts the current functioning state of the organism to make it ready for subsequent action” (Motte, 2009).

Picard maintains that, according to Damasio’s theory on primary emotions, “there are certain features or stimuli in the world that we respond to emotionally first, and which activate a corresponding set of feelings (and cognitive state) secondarily” (Picard, 1997). In this case, no cognitive process seems to be involved, since, in this view, affect can also be elicited without cognitive appraisal (Picard, 2000). A simple example of a primary emotion elicitation could be the startle that arouses upon hearing a loud bang, which is a visceral reaction to a stimulus coming from the environment (Picard, 2000).

These emotions are called also *basic* by Izard, because they “are assumed to have innate neural substrates, innate and universal expressions” (Izard, 1992). Indeed, primary emotions would be elicited by

particular neural circuits, which makes the body respond unconsciously to certain stimuli, activating physiological reactions (for instance, changes in heart rate or endocrine system, sweating, etc.) and expressive reactions (facial expressions), even before the subject is conscious of the emotion he is feeling. When the emotion becomes conscious, we can have an emotional experience, called ‘feeling’ in neuroscience (Christoforidou and Motte, 2009). Although this topic is anything but clear, and still much debated among theorists, this point of view should be taken into account when speaking about emotional responses to products. At least, it could help to avoid confusion when matching the appraisal theory with the evolutionary approach of neuroscience.

Secondary emotions

Secondary, or *cognitive* (Picard, 1997) or *reflective* (Helander and Khalid, 2006) emotions derive from a cognitive elaboration of the stimulus, which is assessed on the basis of different elements, among which user’s concerns, goals, past experiences, memories, cultural and social references. According to appraisal theory, this assessment can occur at an unconscious level, without subject’s control (Desmet and Hekkert, 2007). The resulting emotions, however, are experienced by the subject as conscious feelings. Also secondary emotions may activate involuntary reactions, which are tangible manifestations of the emotion experienced. As Picard (1997) maintains, “cognitive thoughts can arouse emotions that lead to physiological changes”.

Secondary emotions are the type of emotional response usually considered in the study of emotions elicited by products, because they are the emotions we experience consciously and which replace primary emotions, lasting for a longer time in our mind. Secondary emotions are also more subjective than primary emotions, being affected by personal assessments.

It is not simple to clearly separate the elicitation of primary and secondary emotions, since it is still a matter of discussion among scholars in this field. Moreover, the neural processes in consideration lasts milliseconds, thus the differentiation between the two processes in the study of the user response is not relevant in respect to the temporal sequence of what

occurs. The importance of the differentiation between primary and secondary emotions to design research is due to the fact that some stimuli (for instance a particular sound, colour, or smell) might cause the activation of visceral and often unconscious emotional reactions, which may affect the subsequent evaluation of the product and also the emotion we effectively experience (Christoforidou and Motte, 2009).

A COMPREHENSIVE MODEL OF THE USER RESPONSE

The categorization of the three levels of user response makes it possible to deepen their analysis in terms of the way they arise, their relations and the way they can be studied and analysed by researchers (in design or in other disciplines), in order to propose a visual model in which all these aspects are represented.

The first step to create such a model is to understand what occurs between the capture of the stimulus by the senses and the generation of the different levels of response. The construction of the model aims to answer some questions, such as: what is the relation between the three different levels of response (cognitive, affective and hedonic)? At what stage of interaction do emotions emerge? What are they influenced by? Is there a direct relation between the stimulus (the product features) and the emotions elicited, or are they influenced by other factors? Affective neuroscience helps to answer these

questions, since it offers a model of the pathway of the stimulus elaboration in the brain. In particular, it explains how the information is processed by different brain areas, stressing the relations between the areas involved.

The aim of the new suggested model is to overlap the content of the user response (i.e. the three types of responses) to the neurological pathway (i.e. the brain centres involved and their relations).

This comprehensive model underpins the model proposed by LeDoux (1996), adapted by Helander and Khalid (2006) and Christoforidou and Motte (2009).

MODEL STRUCTURE

To create a comprehensive model of the user response, the space was divided on the basis of two criteria: the consciousness of what is occurring (horizontal line) and the kind of reaction, i.e. affective or cognitive (vertical line).

The difference between affect and cognition can be synthetically explained as follows: “whereas affect refers to feeling responses, cognition is used to interpret, make sense of, and understand user experience” (Helander and Khalid, 2006). Thus, on the basis of the two identified axis, the area of the model results divided into four quadrants, each one corresponding to a kind of reaction: cognitive unconscious; cognitive conscious; affective unconscious; affective conscious (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The model structure: the space has been built following two criterions, i.e. the consciousness of the process and its quality (affective or cognitive).

In this space, the whole path from the product perception to the generation of the user response has been traced (Figure 2). In the following section, as the steps of this process are explained, cognitive, emotional and hedonic responses are presented, connected to the brain areas responsible for their generation. The explanation is supported by an example, i.e. how the user responds to the form of a new sport car just bought by a friend, where ‘form’ is intended as the mix of features which can be perceived by the senses (visual, tactile, auditory or olfactory features).

THE PROCESS OF RESPONSE GENERATION

Starting from the left of the diagram, it is possible to follow the process representing how the stimulus coming from the product is captured and elaborated by the brain.

The stimulus, corresponding to one or more product features (the particular smell of new in the car, its red colour, the aerodynamic shape, the motor roar, the soft sound of the closing door, the smooth texture of the leather seats, or a mix of these elements), is captured by the sensory receptors and conducted through the nerves to the thalamus, the first brain

centre reached by nervous impulses. From here, two neurological pathways can be followed: the *low road* and the *high road* (Helander and Khalid, 2006; Christoforidou and Motte, 2009)

Emotional response: primary emotions

In the low road, the signal from thalamus immediately reaches the limbic system and other emotional centres (such as the amygdala, the brain area connected to the emotion of fear). These areas are responsible for detecting stimuli which require the attention of the subject, and for evaluating them in a fast way, for instance to understand if they represent a danger for the subject. This process can be carried out matching the signal to the information residing in specific memory centres, directly connected to the limbic system (Le Doux, 1996; Christoforidou and Motte, 2009).

In this step of the process, primary emotions are elicited, as direct and visceral responses to a stimulus, which automatically activate physiological and expressive reactions. Indeed, the limbic system is directly connected to the hypothalamus (and other centres with similar functions), responsible for the activation of involuntary reactions. These reactions

Figure 2. The model represents the generation of the user response. The three types of response (cognitive, affective and hedonic) are visualized, with relation to the brain areas involved in their elicitation.

can be classified as somatic response (i.e. reflex, startle), endocrine system activation (hormone release – for instance, adrenaline), autonomic responses (i.e. heart rate, sweating, or body temperature), or expressive reactions (i.e. changes in facial or vocal expressions) (Motte, 2009).

Following the example of the sport car, the rumbling sound of the motor might activate, before one is conscious of it, the brain centre connected to fear, the amygdala, provoking an acceleration of the cardiac rhythm, or variations in sweating, and likely making the subject respond also with changes in his facial expressions.

Primary emotions may become conscious, if the signal reaches the prefrontal cortex (the centre of awareness), after activating involuntary reactions. Some scholars maintain that primary emotions may remain unconscious, affecting our evaluations and behaviour without making us aware of them (Izard, 1992). Anyway, they affect cognitive processes of stimulus elaboration, also influencing the generation of secondary emotions.

The low road is the first reaction to the stimulus, faster than the cognitive elaboration, which is however more precise in the signal evaluation (Helander and Khalid, 2006).

Cognitive response

Parallel to the low road, the stimulus is also sent to the cortices, the areas responsible for cognitive elaborations. In brief, the signal reaches the sensory cortex (subdivided into visual, auditory or olfactory cortex, depending on the nature of the signal), where it is pre-processed in order to be recognized and interpreted by the prefrontal cortex. Indeed, the sensory cortex elaborates and organizes signals to make them recognizable for subsequent elaborations. Perceptual and Gestalt theories explain, for instance, the generation of the visual image in the visual cortex (Kanizsa, 1979). It is through these processes that the user, who is looking at the sport car, perceives it as an object, separated from the background and the environment that surrounds it: the visual stimuli coming from the product are grouped together and let the user recognize the object as a unique element. After these elaborations, the signal reaches other areas of the cortex, among which the prefrontal cortex, where it is matched with the hippocampus, the

area of conceptual memory. Here the stimulus is perceived, recognized, interpreted and associated to meanings, memories and past experiences and the subject becomes aware of the stimulus and its meaning. In this step, it is generated the cognitive response, which comprises product's semantics, metaphors, symbolic or product's personality associations (Crilly et al., 2004). Connections with the memory centres explain why this kind of response is highly affected by socio-cultural references and personal past experiences.

Now the user is aware of the object he is looking at, recognizes it as a sport car and, probably, associates it to a specific brand, or to a particular historical period. Moreover, the cognitive elaborations, consequent to the perception of the object, could bring the user to make associations between the car and the idea of luxury, richness and power (symbolic associations), or to interpret the car as high performance, elegant or fast (semantic associations).

Emotional response: secondary emotions

Following the *high road* process, the second type of emotion, cognitive-based, may arise, as the result of a cognitive evaluation of the stimulus on the basis of the user's values, concerns and objectives.

If the user's concerns are richness, power, and high social status, the car, linked to the semantic and symbolic associations previous made, becomes a means to achieve the user's goals, and the object could generate a positive emotion, such as admiration, desire or fascination. (Desmet, 2003)

As the model illustrates, secondary emotions may still reach the limbic system, and physiological and expressive reactions could be activated. According to some scholars, these reactions are difficult to associate to a specific kind of emotion, because they are affected by a lot of external factors (Griffith, 1997; Picard, 2000). Moreover, some complex emotions, as love or grief, do not provoke any physiological reaction.

Despite these difficulties, many studies focus on the analysis of secondary emotions through the evaluation of physiological or expressive reactions (Desmet, 2004; Popa et al., 2010).

Secondary emotion straddles the cognitive and the affective space. Indeed, even though it concerns 'feeling responses', it comes from a cognitive process

of evaluation. The same goes for the *perception* of the primary emotion, which is in part cognitive because it becomes conscious only when it reaches the prefrontal cortex.

Hedonic response

The last level of the user response, dealing with pleasure, is the hedonic one. The three kinds of pleasure proposed, on the basis of Jordan's classification, are added on the map, linked to the NAcc centre (Nucleus Accumbens), which mediates the hedonic sensation. This centre is connected to the MFB (medial forebrain bundle), the desire system (Christoforidou and Motte, 2009). Both these centres are linked to the prefrontal cortex, where, as for primary and secondary emotions, the hedonic sensation becomes conscious.

The first kind of pleasure, physio-pleasure, is linked to the sensory cortices. Indeed, as Ramachandran (1999) argues, a sensation can directly activate the pleasure system, making the subject feel hedonic sensations just as a physical reaction to a pleasant stimulus (Hekkert, 2006). As an example, the smooth surface of the leather seat of the car could elicit a pleasant bodily sensation, connected to the tactile quality of the material.

The second type of pleasure, socio-pleasure, is the result of a conscious or unconscious evaluation of the stimulus on the basis of its social value. For instance, the sport car could be associated with the admiration it may generate in one's friends. As a consequence, the product may activate a pleasurable sensation. For this reason, in the model, socio-pleasure is connected to the cognitive elaborations, in particular to the symbolic associations, which are involved in the assessment of a product's capacity to enhance relations among users, or to strengthen or improve user's social position.

Finally, ideo-pleasure concerns the values conveyed by the product, which are assessed by the user on the basis of his/her own values. Ideo-pleasure can also deal with aesthetic evaluations, which are affected by culture and education. For instance, the appreciation of the line of the car, and its comparison with the older models of the same manufacturer, may be the source of ideo-pleasure, for one particularly interested in the history and evolution of car production. This process is conscious in most cases, because it is the

consequence of a conscious evaluation and reflection over the stimulus.

Ideo-pleasure is strictly connected to the positive cognitive emotion the stimulus might elicit, and, in this case, the two levels of response could in part overlap.

The model proposed is a simplification of what occurs in the generation of the three types of response to product. In reality, they cannot be clearly separated, since they are strictly connected and mutually influenced.

FROM A MODEL TO A MAP

The model proposed could be used for different purposes. As first to give an overview of the main aspects involved in the user response deriving from a non-instrumental interaction, and their relations. Indeed, such a visualization could help researchers and students to more deeply understand the connections between the different levels of the response, how they are generated and the complexity of this area of inquiry. It could also be useful to understand the extension of the Design and Emotion field, which deals with different and interrelated aspects of the user response.

The second aim is to create a tool for researchers in this field, who could use this model as a map where collocate their studies, to understand their positioning in this wide and multi-faceted area of inquiry. By doing so, it would be possible to clarify the positioning of each study in respect to the other areas of the user response; at the same time, this placement can help in clarifying the implications between the subject of one's own study and the related aspects of the user response.

Finally, the map can be used to identify and visualize the main disciplines dealing with the topics related to user-product interaction (Figure 3). This further level is also helpful for researchers, since it could offer an idea of what kind of references, methods and tools can be considered in studying a particular topic. Moreover, it could help to identify the possible collaborations with disciplines different from design, in order to analyse a particular aspect of the user response.

DISCIPLINES INVOLVED

Neuroscience, psychology, affective computing, marketing, neuromarketing, human factors engineering, semantics, anthropology and cultural sociology were visualized on the map with respect to the areas they are mainly interested in. They are just some relevant examples of the disciplines involved in the study of particular aspects of the human-product interaction.

For instance, psychology has developed methods and tools to study the cognitive processes, from perception (perceptual and cognitive psychology) to the meaning association and the emotions elicited by objects, particularly through the use of verbal methods (cognitive psychology). Psychology is also involved in the study of emotions in their expressive manifestation, such as facial expressions (Ekman, 1994).

Affective computing has developed instruments to detect emotions starting from their physiological

manifestations (Picard, 2000).

Marketing is interested in studying the elicitation of pleasure and desire in the users, both sensory, reflective and social pleasure. Moreover, it is interested in exploring the meaning and symbolic associations. A new branch of marketing, neuromarketing, emerged in the last years, as a mix of marketing and neuroscience competences (Lindström, 2008). Its aim is to analyse the consumer's reactions towards products, with a particular attention to the activation of the desire system.

Anthropology and cultural sociology are placed on the area of the memory centres, since they deals with the study of all the cultural and social aspects which may deeply affect the perception and interpretation of products, and which are learned through experience. Human factor engineering is interested in the analysis of how the product is interpreted by the user, relying on methods such as Kansei Engineering, useful in the

Figure 3. Visualization of the main disciplines involved in the study of the user response to products. The area covered by the circles represents the focus of each discipline

analysis of the meanings associated to products (Nagamachi, 1995).

This representation can still be implemented and enriched, but what emerges from this visualization is that disciplines coming both from scientific and humanistic traditions deal with the user response to products, even though, obviously, with different aims and points of view.

THE ROLE OF DESIGN

Finally, the design discipline has strong competences in some areas of this map. Figure 4 shows the areas design is mainly involved in. The full circles represent core competences of design: the control of the product features (e.g. materials, colours, shape, texture, smell); the study of the sensations elicited by the product and their pleasantness; the assessment of the pleasantness of a product in terms of both the aesthetic quality and the values it conveys (reflective pleasure). The empty circles show other areas of interest of design research, which are often analysed in collaboration with external disciplines.

As a consequence, it can be argued that in the study

of the user response, design has strong core competences in some areas, mainly connected to the design practice. In other areas, design research has developed tools and methods basing on the knowledge coming from other disciplines, such as psychology, neuroscience, semantics, or marketing. The interdisciplinary nature of the design discipline is thus visually represented on the map, reinforcing the vision that, as Krippendorff (2006) argues, “one of the most outstanding abilities of designers is to process information from diverse sources and disciplines”.

CONCLUSIONS

The model proposed is an attempt to summarize the existing theories about the user response to product features, in order to create an overview of the aspects involved in the generation of the different types of responses. The visual representation of these aspects allows to identify the complex relations among the three levels of response and what they are influenced by in their elicitation. The relevance of this model for design research would lie in its attempt to

Figure 4. The role of design in the study of the aspects affecting the user response

summarize and clarify the different approaches in the study of the user cognitive and affective response (which bring, for instance, to the differentiation between primary and secondary emotions) and to give an overview of the different disciplines dealing with these topics. Moreover, using the real processes of elaboration of the stimuli as a base for the identification of the different kinds of response, can help to understand how each level of response is activated by the product features.

Apart from supporting a deeper comprehension of the user response, the model could also be used as a research tool by scholars, in particular when approaching this wide field of inquiry. Indeed, the model could be used by researchers as a map to place their own study, in order to clarify the context of their study and the relation with other aspects of the user response.

Finally, the representation of the disciplines involved in the study of particular areas of the map may help to understand which approaches, tools and methods have been developed to investigate each area. This could be very useful for whom interested in the study of this topic from the design point of view, since often design research is concerned with the evaluation of the user response to products, at different levels. The model could also be improved by adding a further layer showing the main literature references, or the most expert scholars, for each discipline or each area of the model. By doing so, it could become a sort of evolving guide in the exploration of this field of inquiry.

LIMITS

The model proposed refers to a particular type of interaction, defined non-instrumental, thus not aimed at the product use. This is a limitation in the model, since aspects concerning product functions, affordability and usability still affects the user response and the emotions elicited. However, the relation between user and product is often strongly affected by the first impression, which has a great impact on the subsequent choices and behaviours towards the object (Crilly et al., 2004).

FURTHER DEVELOPMENTS

The proposed model was created starting from the study of the interaction with physical objects. It may be interesting to investigate the possibility to adapt the

same model to different fields of design (from web design to interior design), to evaluate the user response to diverse design artifacts.

Another possible development of the map could be the creation of sub-models, which explore specific areas of the map, to show, for instance, which kinds of tools or methods can be used in the study of a particular type of response.

Finally, the model could be completed adding the aspects concerning product use, which is another source of emotional response, thus moving from a non-instrumental to an instrumental interaction.

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